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IMPACT OF NON PERFORMING ASSETS ON PROFITABILITY OF BANKS: A STUDY OF HDFC BANK

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ABSTRACT:

Granting of credit for economic activities is the prime duty of banking. Apart from raising resources through fresh deposits, borrowings and recycling of funds received back from borrowers constitute a major part of funding credit dispensation activity. Lending is generally encouraged because it has the effect of funds being transferred from the system to productive purposes, which results into economic growth. However, lending also carries a risk called credit risk, which arises from the failure of borrower. Non-recovery of loans along with interest forms a major hurdle in the process of credit cycle. Thus, these loan losses affect the bank's profitability on a large scale. Though complete elimination of such losses is not possible, but banks can always aim to keep the losses at a low level. Non-Performing Asset (NPA) has emerged since over a decade as an alarming threat to the banking industry in our country sending distressing signals on the sustainability and insurability of the affected banks. The positive results of the chain of measures affected under banking reforms by the Government of India and RBI in terms of the two Narasimhan Committee Reports in this contemporary period have been neutralized by the ill effects of this surging threat. Despite various correctional steps administered to solve and end this problem, concrete results are eluding. It is a sweeping and all pervasive virus confronted universally on banking and financial institutions. Main aim of any person is the utilization of money in the best manner since the India is country where more than half of the population has problem of running the family in the most efficient manner. However Indian people faced large number of problem till the development of the full-fledged banking sector. The Indian banking sector has really helped the Indian people to utilize the single money in the best manner as they want. People now have started investing their money in the banks and banks also provide goods returns on the deposited amount. The people now have

at the most understood that banks provide them good security to their deposits and so excess amounts are invested in the banks. Thus, banks have helped the people to achieve their socio economic objectives.

Keywords: *Nonperforming Assets, Asset, HDFC Bank, India. Private Sector Banks*

INTRODUCTION:

Asset:

An asset is a resource with economic value that an individual, corporation or country owns or controls with the expectation that it will provide future benefit.

Non-Performing Assets:

Meaning

An asset is classified as non-performing asset (NPAs) if dues in the form of principal and interest are not paid by the borrower for a period of 180 days. However, with effect from March 2004, default status would be given to a borrower if dues are not paid for 90 days. If any advance or credit facilities granted by bank to a borrower become non-performing, then the bank will have to treat all the advances/credit facilities granted to that borrower as non-performing without having any regard to the fact that there may still exist certain advances/credit facilities having performing status.

Need and Importance of NPA

NPA's prudential norms and regulations are basically aimed at ensuring the safety and soundness of the financial system, imparting of greater transparency and accountability in operation and restoring creditability in Indian Financial System.

Prudential norms serve two primary purposes, which are:

- 1) Bringing out the true position of a bank's loan profitability.
- 2) Help arrest its deterioration

A proper system made for NPA's helps in:

- 1) Income recognition
- 2) Classification of assets, and
- 3) Provisioning for bad debts on prudential basis is necessary if balance sheet of a bank is to reflect its original financial health.

Need of the Study

- Understanding the causes of NPA.
- To get knowledge about how to solve the problem of NPA.
- To understand effects of NPA on banks.
- To study which preventive measures are taken to reduce NPA in bank?

Objectives of the Study

- To understand the concept of non-performing assets.
- To understand impact of non-performing assets on bank's profitability.
- To study the procedure for identification of non-performing assets.
- To study asset quality of non-performing assets in HDFC Bank.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Research Objectives

- ❖ To understand the concept of non-performing assets.
- ❖ To understand impact of non-performing assets on bank's profitability.
- ❖ To study the procedure for identification of non-performing assets.
- ❖ To study asset quality of non-performing assets in HDFC Bank.

Scope of the Study

The scope of this project report is only limited for HDFC Bank. This project report helps to understand the concept of non-performing assets

Research Design

The research design for this study is analytical. Because researcher utilized the number of data of HDFC Bank.

Data Collection

The researcher has collected information from both the sources i.e. primary and secondary.

Primary Data

For collecting primary data, observation and discussion method is used like discussion with branch manager and staff associated with loan department.

Secondary Data

Secondary data refers to the data, which has been already generated and is available for use. The data about NPAs, classification of loan assets and advances of bank is taken from annual reports and website of HDFC Bank.

Sources of Secondary Data

- 1) Annual reports of HDFC Bank from previous 3 years
- 2) RBI website
- 3) Books

Tools Used for Analyzing Data

The data collected with the help of statistical tools like ratio analysis. Tables are used to represent the consolidated data. Graphical presentation is also used for better comprehension and

presentation.

DATA ANALYSIS:

1) Total Assets of HDFC Bank

Table No.1

Year Ending On	Amount (In Rs. Crore)
31.03.2019	146019
31.03.2020	160957
31.03.2021	159324

Chart No.1

Interpretation: Above chart indicates that total assets of bank in the year 2019 was 146019 Crores. Then total assets of bank were increased in the year 2020 by 9.28% i.e. 160957 Crores but it can have decreased in the year2021 by 1.02% i.e. 159324 Crores.

2) Gross Non-Performing Assets of HDFC Bank

Table No.2

Year Ending On	Amount (In Rs. Crore)
31.03.2019	6402
31.03.2020	10386
31.03.2021	17189

Chart No. 2

Interpretation:

Above chart indicates that gross non-performing assets of bank in the year 2019 was 6402 Crores. Then it was increased in the year 2020 and 2021 by 38.35% and 39.57% respectively.

3) Net Non-Performing Assets of HDFC Bank

Table No.3

Year Ending On	Amount (In Rs. Crore)
31.03.2019	4127
31.03.2020	6832
31.03.2021	11230

Chart No. 3

Interpretation:

Above chart indicates that net non-performing assets of bank in the year 2019 was 4127 Crores. Then net non-performing assets of bank was increased in the year 2020 by 39.59% and again it is increase in the year 2021 by 39.16%.

4) Total Advances of HDFC Bank

Table No. 4

Year Ending On	Amount (In Rs. Crore)
31.03.2019	98599
31.03.2020	107563
31.03.2021	95515

Chart No. 4

Interpretation:

From the above chart, researcher observe that advances of bank in the year 2020 was 95899 Crores. It was increased in the year 2021 by 8.34% i.e. 107563 Crores but it again decreased in the year 2022 by 12.61% i.e. 95515 Crores.

5) Gross Advances OfHDFC Bank

Table No. 5

Year Ending On	Amount (In Rs. Crore)
31.03.2019	101210
31.03.2020	111240
31.03.2021	101537

Chart No. 5

Interpretation:

From the above chart, researcher observe that gross advances of bank in the year 2019 was 101210 Crores. It was increased in the year 2020 by 9.01% but it again decreased in the year 2021 by 9.55% i.e. 101537 Crores.

6) Gross NPA Ratio (Gross NPA as % to Gross Advances)

Gross NPA ratio is the ratio of gross NPA to gross advances of the bank. Gross NPA is the sum of all loan assets that are classified as NPA as per RBI guidelines. The ratio is to be counted in terms of percentage and the formula for gross NPA is as follows:

$$\text{Gross NPA Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross NPA}}{\text{Gross Advances}} * 100$$

Table No. 6

Year Ending On	Gross NPAs (In Rs. Cr.)	Gross Advances (In Rs. Cr.)	Gross NPA Ratio (%)
31.03.2019	6402	101210	6.33
31.03.2020	10386	111240	9.34
31.03.2021	17189	101537	16.93

Chart No. 6

Interpretation: From the above chart, we can observe that gross NPA ratio of bank in the year 2019 was 6.33%. It was increased in the year 2020 and 2021 at 9.34% and 16.93% respectively.

7) Net NPA Ratio (Net NPA as % to Net Advances)

The net NPA is the ratio of net NPA to net advances in which the provision is to be deducted from the gross advances. The provision is to be made for NPA account. The formula for that is:

$$\text{Net NPA Ratio} = \frac{\text{Net NPA}}{\text{Net Advances}} * 100$$

$$\text{Net NPA} = \text{Gross NPA} - \text{Provision}$$

Table No. 7

Year Ending On	Net NPAs (In Rs. Cr.)	Net Advances (In Rs. Cr.)	Net NPA Ratio (%)
31.03.2019	4127	98599	4.19
31.03.2020	6832	107563	6.35
31.03.2021	11230	95515	11.76

Chart No. 7

Interpretation:

From the above chart, we can observe that net NPA ratio of bank in the year 2019 was 4.19%. It was increased in the year 2020 and 2021 at 6.35% and 11.76% respectively.

8) Provision Ratio

Provisions are made to keep safely against the NPA, and it directly effect on the gross profit of the banks. The provision ratio is nothing but total provision held for NPA to gross NPA of the banks. The formula for that is:

$$\text{Provision Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Provision}}{\text{Gross NPAs}} * 100$$

Net NPA = Gross NPA - Provision

Therefore, Provision = Gross NPA - Net NPA

Table No. 8

Year Ending On	Total Provision (In Rs. Cr.)	Gross NPAs (In Rs. Cr.)	Provision Ratio (%)
31.03.2019	2275	6402	35.53%
31.03.2020	3554	10386	34.21%
31.03.2021	5959	17189	34.67%

Chart No. 8

Interpretation:

From the above chart, we can observe that provision ratio of bank in the year 2019 was 35.53%. It was increased in the year 2020 and 2021 at 34.21% and 34.67% respectively.

9) Problem Asset Ratio

It is the ratio of gross NPA to total asset of the bank. The formula for this ratio is:

$$\text{Problem Asset Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross NPAs}}{\text{Total Assets}} * 100$$

Table No. 9

Year Ending On	Gross NPAs (In Rs. Cr.)	Total Assets (In Rs. Cr.)	Problem Asset Ratio (%)
31.03.2019	6402	146019	4.38
31.03.2020	10386	160957	6.45
31.03.2021	17189	159324	10.78

Chart No. 9

Interpretation:

From the above chart, we can observe that problem asset ratio of bank in the year 2019 was 4.38%. It was increased in the year 2020 and 2021 at 6.45% and 10.78% respectively.

10) Sub-Standard Assets Ratio

The sub-standard assets ratio indicates the scope for improvement in NPA. The higher the ratio, the better is position of recovering the advances. The variations in the sub-standard assets ratio are caused by the higher percentage of doubtful assets over the sub-standard assets in the banks. The formula for sub-standard assets is:-

$$\text{Sub - Standard Assets Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Sub - Standard Assets}}{\text{Gross NPAs}} * 100$$

Table No. 10

Year Ending On	Sub-Standard Assets (In Rs. Cr.)	Gross NPAs (In Rs. Cr.)	Sub-Standard Assets Ratio (%)
31.03.2019	2975	6402	46.47
31.03.2020	5342.55	10386	51.44
31.03.2021	5294.21	17189	30.8

Chart No. 10

Interpretation: Above chart shows that in the year 2019, ratio of sub-standard assets was 46.47%. The it was increased in the year 2020 at 51.44%. So it was good for bank. But ratio is again decreased in the year 2021 at 30.8% so it is not good for bank for achieving better position and recovering advances also.

11) Doubtful Assets Ratio

The doubtful assets ratio indicates the portion of total doubtful assets to gross NPAs. If the ratio is higher, there is more scope for compromising and reducing NPAs. Doubtful assets are divided into following 3 categories:

11.1) Ratio for Doubtful 1 Assets are as follows:

$$\text{Doubtful 1 Assets Ratio} = \frac{\text{Doubtful 1 Assets}}{\text{Gross NPAs}} * 100$$

Table No 11.1

Year Ending On	Doubtful 1 Assets (In Rs. Cr.)	Gross NPAs (In Rs. Cr.)	Doubtful 1 Assets Ratio (%)
31.03.2019	1830.97	6402	28.6
31.03.2020	2280.76	10386	21.96
31.03.2021	6652.14	17189	38.7

Chart No 11.1

Interpretation:

Above chart shows that in the year 2019, doubtful 1 assets ratio was 28.6%. The ratio was decreased in the year 2020 at 21.96%. But ratio is again increased in the year 2021 at 38.7%.

11.2) Ratio for Doubtful 2 Assets are as follows:

$$\text{Doubtful 2 Assets Ratio} = \frac{\text{Doubtful 2 Assets}}{\text{Gross NPAs}} * 100$$

Table No 11.2

Year Ending On	Doubtful 2 Assets (In Rs. Cr.)	Gross NPAs (In Rs. Cr.)	Doubtful 2 Assets Ratio (%)
31.03.2019	527.52	6402	8.24
31.03.2020	2126.01	10386	20.47
31.03.2021	4589.46	17189	26.7

Chart No 11.2

Interpretation:

Above chart shows that in the year 2019, doubtful 2 assets ratio was 8.24%. The ratio was increased in the year 2020 and 2021 at 20.47% and 26.7% respectively.

11.3) Ratio for Doubtful 3 Assets are as follows:

$$\text{Doubtful 3 Assets Ratio} = \frac{\text{Doubtful 3 Assets}}{\text{Gross NPAs}} * 100$$

Table No 11.3

Year Ending On	Doubtful 3 Assets (In Rs. Cr.)	Gross NPAs (In Rs. Cr.)	Doubtful 3 Assets Ratio (%)
31.03.2019	16.64	6402	0.26
31.03.2020	93.47	10386	0.9
31.03.2021	476.13	17189	2.77

Chart No 11.3

Interpretation:

Above chart shows that in the year 2019, doubtful 3 assets ratio was 0.26%. The ratio was decreased in the year 2020 at 0.9%. But ratio is again increased in the year 2021 at 2.77%.

12) Loss Assets Ratio

Loss assets ratio shows the proportion of loss that the banks are likely to suffer as compared to Gross NPAs. The ratio must be minimum, as it will indicate the assets to be lost would be lower as compared to Gross NPAs. The formula for loss assets is:

$$\text{Loss Assets Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Loss Asset}}{\text{Gross NPAs}} * 100$$

Table No.12

Year Ending On	Loss Assets (In Rs. Cr.)	Gross NPAs (In Rs. Cr.)	Loss Assets Ratio (%)
31.03.2019	1051.84	6402	16.43
31.03.2020	543.18	10386	5.23
31.03.2021	177.04	17189	1.03

Chart No 12

Interpretation: Above chart shows that in the year 2019, loss assets ratio was 16.43%. The ratio was decreased in the year 2020 and 2021 at 5.23% and 1.03% respectively.

13) Classification of Non-Performing Assets In HDFC Bank As On 31.03.2019

Chart No 13

Interpretation

Above pie chart indicates that sub-standard assets, doubtful 1 assets, doubtful 2 assets, doubtful 3 assets and loss assets in bank as on 31.03.2019 are 46.47%, 28.60%, 8.24%, 0.26% and 16.43% respectively.

14) Classification of Non-Performing Assets in HDFC Bank as On 31.03.2020

Chart No 14

Interpretation

Above pie chart indicates that sub-standard assets, doubtful 1 asset, doubtful 2 assets, doubtful 3 assets and loss assets in bank as on 31.03.2020 are 51.44%, 21.96%, 20.47%, 0.90% and 5.23% respectively.

15) Classification of Non-Performing Assets in HDFC Bank as On 31.03.2021

Chart No 15

Interpretation

Above pie chart indicates that sub-standard assets, doubtful 1 asset, doubtful 2 assets, doubtful 3 assets and loss assets in bank as on 31.03.2021 are 30.8%, 38.7%, 26.7%, 2.77% and 1.03% respectively.

16) NPA % of Different Loan Schemes as On 31st March, 2021

Table No .16

PARTICULARS	NPA (%)
Super Housing Loan Scheme	2.72
Super Car Loan Scheme and Vehicle Loan Scheme	4.89
Model Education Loan Scheme	5.87
Top up Loan Scheme	2.00
Gold Loan Scheme	2.80
Aadhar Loan Scheme	0.68

Chart No. 16

Interpretation

In the year 2021,

- NPA in Super Housing Loan Scheme is 2.72%
- NPA in Super Car Loan Scheme and Vehicle Loan Scheme is 4.89%
- NPA in Model Education Loan Scheme is 5.87%
- NPA in Top Up Loan Scheme is 2%
- NPA in Gold Loan Scheme is 2.80%
- NPA in Aadhar Loan Scheme is 0.68%

FINDINGS & SUGGESTIONS

Findings:

1) NPA is in existence under the category of

- Super Housing Loan Scheme
- Super Car Loan Scheme and Vehicle Loan Scheme

- Model Education Loan Scheme
- Top Up Loan Scheme
- Gold Loan Scheme
- Aadhar Loan Scheme

2) In case of ratios,

- From previous 3 years gross NPA ratio are continuously increasing so it indicates low credit portfolio of bank.
- Net NPA ratio are also increasing from previous 3 years so it indicates high quantity of risky assets in bank.
- Ratio for sub-standard assets are low as compared to previous year. Lower ratio indicates that bank is not in better position for recovering the advances.
- Ratio for doubtful assets are higher as compared to previous year 2016 so there is more scope for compromising and reducing NPAs.
- Loss assets ratio of bank is minimum so it will indicate assets to be lost would be lower as compared to gross NPAs.

CONCLUSION

India is a developing country. So, for continuity in its development it can prefer non-zero level of NPAs. As the name suggests itself NPAs are those assets which never generate profit to bank and threats for bank. Bank should try their best to manage these non-ceasing assets or never try to remove or terminate. Because it is very difficult to vanish these assets. The NPAs adversely affect profits and financial viability of bank. Compromise is one of the measures to reduce the NPAs. It has its limitations and may have adverse effects and hence has to be used judiciously with proper understanding of the genuine problems and concerns of each other.

To conclude this study researcher can say about this report is that?

Bank shows very much high NPA ratios,

NPAs represent high level of risk and low level of credit appraisal,

There are so many preventive measures available to stop an asset or account becoming NPA.

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